

H-Index / Citation / i10 index Details of

International Journal of Embedded Systems and Applications (IJESA)

ISSN : 1839-5171

<https://wireilla.com/ijesa/indexing.html>

Google Scholar Citation

Cited by

	All	Since 2015
Citations	553	457
h-index	8	7
i10-index	7	5

<https://scholar.google.com.au/citations?user=JNut-KYAAAAJ&hl=en>

All

Since 2015

Citations	553	457
h-index	8	7
i10-index	7	5